

Contextualizing Ghana's land right issues and the role for a blockchain based solution: a research report

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Abstract

One in three people living throughout Western and Central Africa fear that they will lose their homes, or the lands that they have lived and worked on, within the next five years due to poor record keeping practices and challenging bureaucratic processes for protecting rights-holders claims to land. Similar fears can be found in Ghana where the two land administration systems do not communicate well with each other. Where traditional processes are necessary to acquire land rights on the majority of land in Ghana, the state system does not formally recognize the records generated by those processes. This means that the responsibility falls to the individual to navigate these complex systems and complete the necessary steps to satisfy both.

Landano is addressing these challenges through a decentralized application (dApp) that mints land right records as non-fungible tokens (NFTs) on the Cardano blockchain. The project has designed its system with ongoing stakeholder input, especially at the community level where partnerships have been formed with community leaders and the people that they support. The land rights records that Landano creates have been designed to be compliant with international record-keeping standards and local land laws with the goal of enabling new decentralized finance (DeFi) opportunities for formerly undocumented rights-holders. Countries with pluralistic legal systems like Ghana provide a unique opportunity for a platform like Landano to bridge the gap between centralized government registry systems and the decentralized land administration practiced by traditional community leaders.

Introduction

One in three people living throughout Western and Central Africa fear that they will lose their homes, or the lands that they have lived and worked on, within the next five years ([1]Tabary, 2018). These are legitimate and rational fears, as large areas of land throughout Western and Central Africa remain unregistered. And with the rapid increase of development projects pouring into these countries, the need to ensure that those holding the rights to these properties have them registered is becoming an increasingly vital step to protecting rights-holder's claim to land and to the prevention of the mass displacement of individuals from their traditional homelands. It is no surprise then that Individuals living throughout Ghana are looking to ensure that their claims to land are properly documented and secure. In a 2016 survey of land owners in Ghana, 100% of participants were in favor of modernizing the title registration process in order to develop a well-functioning digitized system ([2]Ehwi and Asante, 2016).

Landano seeks to take part in this modernization process by partnering with stakeholders on the ground in Ghana. Through these partnerships, the project has created a minimum viable product (mvp) as a proof-of-concept decentralized application (dApp) that mints land right

records as non-fungible tokens (NFTs) on the Cardano blockchain. The Processes by which this happens and their outputs have been meticulously designed to maintain compliance with international record-keeping standards and local land laws with the goal of enabling new decentralized finance (DeFi) opportunities for formerly undocumented rights-holders. This will be accomplished by increasing access and safeguarding record authenticity. The benefits of these deliverables are many-fold and studies show that the fear of displacement from traditional land and homes has had both physical and psychological impacts on rights-holders, while also suggesting that increased and legitimized home ownership rates correspond with improved long standing health conditions ([3]Munford, et al., 2020). In this vein, home ownership can be seen as more than just an asset, but one which can empower rights-holders and their communities when secured and utilized. Promoting formalized land ownership within societies not only ensures healthy communities but also serves as a form of poverty alleviation. Both these identified challenges fall in with the United Nations Sustainable Development goals ([4]United Nations, 2015) and thus are global priorities to tackle.

However, Land administration and registration is a major challenge that includes complex policies, informal decision making processes, and legacy systems. These challenges have manifested throughout Ghana's pluralistic legal, and land management, systems. And while an array of solutions have been proposed to address the lack of land security in Western and Central Africa, many have taken a top-down approach. This removes community members from the designing, planning, and implementation processes. Countries with pluralistic legal systems like Ghana provide a unique opportunity to bridge the gap between centralized government registry systems and the decentralized land administration practiced by traditional community leaders. Landano is meeting this opportunity by utilizing a bottom-up design approach, informed by individuals on-the-ground, which has ensured social buy-in and interest in the proposed solution within partner communities. Landano has designed a system to connect records generated through the traditional land allocation processes with the federal Land Commission system and the corresponding registration, or "perfection," procedures.

This Modernization of the land registration system is only one step towards addressing the current challenges presented in Ghana's land administration and registrations systems. It's imperative that Communities are involved in the process as well; from the mapping of community lands, their allocation, and the standardization of administrative processes, these are areas of focus that Landano is actively partnering with communities in Ghana to find solutions for. And that participation has resulted in a system that allows property owners to manage land records for their property through an easy to use interface that also allows access to their geographic information through partnerships made with other projects working in Ghana's Geographic Information System (GIS) sector.

For too long the processes of generating and storing land records has been opaque and inaccessible to citizens around the world. Landano is leveraging decentralized technologies to create an Africa-focused solution that utilizes blockchain to improve transparency and immutability as well as prevent fraud. This innovative approach to record-keeping offers an alternative to individuals seeking to establish formalized ownership over their home and lands. This paper will provide a technical primer, the Landano solution, its current pilot project in

Ghana, outline benefits to ensuring tenure security, and provide a jurisdictional scan of Ghana's land registration and administrative processes.

Technical Primer

First proposed in 2008, implemented in 2009, and continually built upon since, blockchain technologies have rapidly asserted themselves as a trustless alternative to many legacy record keeping systems which are dependent on a centralized authority ([5]Nakamoto; [6]Lemieux, 2017, 1437). Like a public ledger, blockchains record a series of transactions, the participating entities, timestamps, etc. However, unlike conventional systems for recording transactions, which require a third party for validation and thereby suffer from the inefficiencies or costs of that bottleneck, blockchains do not rely on that validation mechanism but instead leverage consensus algorithms to guarantee the consistency of their data ([7]Li et al., 2021; [8]Zheng et al., 2017).

In blockchain systems, committed transactions are recorded within a sequence of “blocks”. These blocks are a combination of transactional data, with the hash of the previous (parent) block recorded in their header ([8]Zheng et al., 2017, 558). This allows each block to “point” back to the record of transactions that preceded it and results in the construction of a chain by which the technology earns its name. Because these chains are continuously growing, utilize a consensus mechanism to append new blocks, and each point back to their predecessor with a unique hash, they are considered immutable. In order to alter a transaction after it has been committed, an attacker needs to re-commit the necessary computational effort of appending all blocks to which the target transaction points. This feature of the blockchain also lends itself to auditability.

While these systems have been, and continue to be, primarily leveraged for enabling decentralized financial transactions, there is global interest in utilizing innovative technologies in other tangentially related fields such as land administration ([9]Augustinus, 2020; [10] Mintah et al., 2020). This is because the land sector, owing to its historically centralized design, especially in the Global South is susceptible to unreliable record keeping practices, the multiple sale of land parcels, and issues tracing ownership ([11]Mintah et al., 2021, 3). All of these weaknesses of centralized legacy systems are challenges that blockchain technologies were designed to address. The incorporation of these technologies into the land sector has the potential to promote sustainable development with reduced risk of fraud as they are secure by design ([12]Khan et al., 2019, 127).

The Landano project aims to offer a solution to these challenges by creating a trustworthy land record system on top of the Cardano protocol which can be offered to countries that are struggling to provide secure land tenure rights. The project leverages a decentralized record keeping system that creates, archives, and validates land right records by minting them as Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs). These tokens are unique digital assets which can be representative of various types of property, whose ownership is embedded in their coding to aid in traceability ([13]Rehman et al., 2021), and which can be aligned with local cultural practices as well as laws for land administration and digital evidence. The system also provides strong guarantees of

authenticity through its compliance with international standards for record-keeping and decentralized identity.

The Landano system introduces an innovative real estate use case to the Cardano community and will be commercially sustainable based on a transaction-fee model. The project has also established working relationships with government officials in local land registry offices in order to ensure proper design of the system and the efficacy of its records.

The Landano Solution

Landano's goal is to bridge customary land management practices with official registry systems through world class record keeping practices; these records will be used as proofs and collateral for decentralized financing (DeFi) products offered to land rights-holders. This utility makes Landano a decentralized implementation of Hernando De Soto's "Mystery of Capital" thesis wherein he claims that capitalism functions poorly without access to credit, and that possession of assets has not been the issue, but that the possession of those assets having been secured informally, can in many cases bar their use as collateral ([14]De Soto, 2000). Put differently, when rights-holders can prove clear ownership or rights to land through authentic and reliable records, they stand to benefit from numerous economic advantages, including access to credit. Because of this, Landano stands to make a significant impact on the economic development of the locations where this dApp is implemented.

However, Landano is not the first with the goal to leverage blockchain for land administration processes; many other projects around the world have attempted and failed to gain traction not only with government partners but with the communities expected to use the technology. Landano wants to provide technology and services to address this gap. The introduction of blockchain enabled land governance cannot be solely implemented from the top down. Where centralized and traditional governance, forcing a top-down registry approach have failed to adequately meet the needs of its citizens, the Landano strategy instead utilizes a grassroots bottom-up approach. Project development has been informed at every stage by on the ground communication with community leaders— who are responsible for several of the initial land registration steps that their citizens must undergo. Project development has also benefited from a commitment to research, which has enabled the development of a holistic understanding of the socio-cultural and regulatory landscape in Ghana. While system design is informed by local laws and land administration regulations, Landano has purposefully designed its solution to accommodate end users.

It's important to note that Landano is not attempting to replace or bypass existing federal registry systems. Landano seeks to develop the bridge between customary and state land tenure processes by safeguarding authentic land rights and improving the reliability of land administration records. Landano is designed to connect records generated through the traditional land allocation processes with the federal Land Commission system and the corresponding registration or "perfection" procedures. However, whether the Landano user decides to complete this formalization stage or not, the Landano records themselves are designed to serve as trustworthy artifacts of the constitutional land allocation decisions made by community leaders.

Partnerships with stakeholders on the ground in Ghana has been a key strategy for guaranteeing that the Landano system has been designed with the perspectives of those it is being built for; Landano has partnered with the Ghanaian chapter of Wada.org which has led to key local team hires and institutional partnerships with the local Cardano blockchain and geographic information system (GIS) community, including Aidblock (formerly The Institute for Liberty and Policy Innovation), Digital Earth Africa, IAMX, Terra Firma in Mozambique, and the Ghana Geospatial Society. Landano has been conducting field research and dAPP minimum viable product (MVP) development since March 2022. The MVP is a proof-of-concept that shows how Landano creates and archives a key set of records that are critical to traditional land right allocation practices. These records include land parcel surveys, allocation notes, lease contracts, and others. These records have been identified as critical proofs of a right-holders claim and Landano has developed a way to structure these records so that they can be used for decentralized finance (DeFi) services. This will allow Landano users to leverage their land right records for financing opportunities like mortgages and business loans.

Landano accomplishes this record structure by creating a non-fungible token (NFT) on Cardano for each land parcel and each corresponding land right document. The supporting digital files for each NFT are stored as a standards-compliant archival package on the Arweave decentralized storage platform. Landano implemented the first of these Landano land right NFTs on Cardano Testnet in December 2022. Mainnet production deployment is currently set for Q3 2023.

The Landano solution provides a convenient web, and smartphone, interface to create and retrieve these records, including geospatial cadastral data associated with each land parcel. However, use of this interface is not required for access of these records as the system is truly decentralized in the sense that all records can be accessed directly via Cardano and Arweave nodes and block explorers, independently from Landano.

The Landano mission is to mint cheap and reliable land right records as Cardano NFTs. This is a practical means to a beneficial end. These trustworthy Landano records will serve as collateral and equity for new DeFi lending opportunities for marginalized communities that previously had very limited financial service options. Therefore, Landano stands to make a significant impact on social and financial inclusion for a wide range of previously undocumented, unbanked individuals. In order to make this a reality, Landano will provide a bridge between existing government systems and customary land administration practices. The records created have been designed to be compliant with local land and evidence laws. The long-term strategy of Landano is to demonstrate its best-of-breed status as a next-generation decentralized land administration system and to provide value to government systems through integration.

Hiawu Besease Case Study

The two land administration systems within Ghana, the federal and traditional, do not communicate well with each other. Traditional processes are necessary to acquire land rights on

the majority of land in Ghana. However, the state system does not formally recognize the records generated by those processes. Instead, the responsibility falls to the individual rights-holders to navigate these complex systems and complete the necessary steps to satisfy both. Landano is addressing these challenges and others identified within Ghana's Land Administration and Registration systems by allowing property owners to manage land records for their real estate property via its easy-to-use [dApp](#) and the partnerships made with projects within the geographic information system network in Ghana and abroad. Through Landano, rights holders will be able to map, store, and organize information about their land.

Early in the project Landano pivoted from its initial plans of working to resolve real estate informality and the rental market in urban Accra, Ghana to working with a traditional village chief and his representatives. To that end, Landano has been conducting its pilot project in Ghana for the past few months ([15]Landano, 2022). Ghana is a West African country that is home to approximately 31 million people, and is rich in coastal savannahs, tropical rain forests, and natural resources. Ghana has been one of the more stable and democratic countries in the region. It has played a major role in inter-continental trade for many centuries and was the first sub-Saharan country to gain its national independence.

The township of Hiawu Besease, in the Ashanti region, was selected as Landano's pilot community. This decision was made for two reasons. The first, and most important, was that after meeting with community leadership, it became clear to the team that the tribal chiefs actively advocate for their community members. Where some customary authorities have prioritized policy focused on personal profit, the leaders of Hiawu Besease have not unilaterally sold or leased land out from under community members in favor of investor groups. Instead, the communal land has been distributed to the families according to their immediate needs. The second reason for the pilot decision was due to Hiawu Besease's unique situation regarding the absence of customary land right records as claimed by the community leaders. This was confirmed by a trip to the main Land Commission Office in Accra, the capital of Ghana, where the Landano team was informed that no data concerning the township could be found; a second trip to the Ashanti regional office hit another dead end— in order to execute a cadastral search to ascertain whether any survey records existed for the community, the team was required to furnish a registered title of a land parcel within the township. A record which doesn't exist.

Given that the customary authorities had claimed that an allocation process had never formally been administered within the township, coupled with the apparent lack of state data, and the need to determine a boundary for the township in order to progress with the implementation of the allocation process, Landano partnered with the community to conduct its own land survey. This process was made possible by the relationships previously developed with Hiawu Besease's customary authorities, and it was with this support that Landano was able to successfully conduct the survey while utilizing both technologically appropriate resources and the local understanding of boundaries supplied by Landano partners. In terms of the MVP development, this accomplishment meant that the cadastral map data utilized within Landano is for previously unsurveyed plots in Ghana.

With the survey outputs, Hiawu Besease will serve as Landano's region of interest (ROI) and will benefit from detailed data extraction as the project progresses with the potential to

secure their allocation records on the blockchain. The results from this process has allowed Landano to strategically position itself as an effective bridge between customary and state land tenure systems.

The Landano architecture is designed to comply with the Ghana Lands Act, Ghanaian digital evidence requirements, and international ISO standards for record-keeping. It supports use cases for land administrators, rights-holders, and rights-seekers. Landano creates and archives a key set of records that are critical to traditional land right allocation practices, namely:

- land parcel surveys and site plans with map plots
- audio-visual recordings of land right allocations by community leaders
- allocation note records
- indenture documents
- lease contracts

And while Formal land registration provides opportunity for economic mobility and autonomy, Landano believes that Individuals deserve to have easy access to their land records and should not face institutionalized push back and bureaucracy. With the development of decentralized systems, like Landano, individuals are empowered to record and securely store their own land records. Landano aims to develop a more holistic view of the nuanced complexity in registering customary land parcels while simultaneously identifying areas where the project will become a legally informed and culturally approved value-add.

For the community leaders who partnered with Landano, the solution offers a way for chiefs to issue their land rights documents more efficiently and more reliably while providing a central transaction database. For the community members and land rights-holders, Landano safeguards their records and establishes a timeline which points to the rightful owner and their progress through the land administration system.

Introduction to Land Management

Land administration and registration processes in Ghana are complex. Characterized by its legal pluralism ([16]Ghana, 2003, 4; [10]Mintah et al., 2020, 148), developing a registration process to accommodate both public and customary land has failed to gain traction since Ghana's independence ([17]Ibid, 149). Public lands are characterized by the state's ownership, management, and control over land. This represents approximately 18% of the total land in Ghana ([18]Yeboah and Shaw, 2013, 22). Section 18, sub points 1 and 2, of the Constitution of Ghana provides a framework for government agencies seeking to acquire private land.

Conversely, customary land is held in trust and governed by traditional leaders, chiefs, and clans on behalf of their people. An allodial title proves ownership of a collective group, for example a family, and is designated by a skin or a stool ([19]Bugri and Yeboah, 2017, 18). The terms stool and skin symbolize the authority of chiefs throughout Ghana; with stool as the preferred term in the Southern regions and with skin as the preferred term in Northern regions ([20]Bukari, 2016, 3). These lands, depending on the location in Ghana, are colloquially referred to as stool, skin, clan, and family lands. They make up about 80% of all land in Ghana ([21]LandLinks, 2013). In all cases, these lands are held by their respective authority on behalf

of the community. Those receiving rights in these lands don't actually own their land outright but lease them from the customary authority who holds the interest. In this tradition, land is a spiritual and physical embodiment of the people who reside on it.

The mix of colonial regulatory systems and traditional, customary systems of governance pose challenges for those seeking to formally register their land. Therefore, unregistered land is governed by customary norms and cultural customs and registered land is governed by bureaucratic systems and institutionalized organization. This can cause major barriers for those seeking to formally register their previously unregistered land. Thus leaving individuals in a frustrating and unclear position about how to engage in these processes.

Benefits to Tenure Security

Lack of tenure security has a knock-on effect on what individuals do with their assets - whether that's investing in better crops and farm equipment, building new structures, or renovating a family shop. In fact, the lack of trustworthy land right records has proven to be the primary barrier that is preventing impoverished people from improving their financial condition ([14] De Soto, 2000). Proving clear ownership or rights to land through authentic and reliable records has numerous economic advantages. These include safeguarding assets from conflicting claims, the ability to sell one's rights in land, and access to lending opportunities such as mortgages. Mortgage markets are especially important to financial mobility as they allow individuals to gain access to loans by securitizing their real property. This has proven to be one of the primary catalysts associated with economic growth in developed economies all around the world ([22]Rose & Noah, 2019).

Registered titles provide two major pathways towards economic stability which include increased security of ownership and collateral for a bank loan ([2]Ehwi and Asante 2016). First security of ownership increases the demand for investment in the property, More investment in the property leads to higher output per square acre of the property. This increases the land price and income derived from the property. Second, using land as collateral for a bank loan creates more supply of cheaper long-term and short-term credit opportunities. Longer term loans bolster more investment into the property. While shorter term loans generate more variable input usage. In both circumstances, individuals are able to leverage their formally registered land as a means as a tool for economic mobility that was previously unavailable to them.

Registering Land in Ghana

The regulatory environment for those in Ghana seeking to register land is riddled with a maze of bureaucratic processes and documentation. Individuals looking to own land must undertake a lengthy and inefficient process to ensure that their land is legally recognized. This involves four major steps in the application process which include understanding who can own land, conveyancing, establishing a sufficient root of title, and using correct, approved instruments.

Land Ownership

Two parameters regarding land ownership in Ghana focus on the amount of time the land is held and who is able to hold the land. Under Ghana's constitution, Article 266(1), only individuals from Ghana can own land. However, under Article 266(4), foreign individuals are able to rent land for up to 50 years with the ability to renew the lease after expiration ([23]Ghana Constitution, 1992). For Ghanaians seeking to own or lease land, they must decide what type of land they are looking for. There are five major types of land with specific acquisition processes for each category. These major types include Stool or Customary Land, Government or State Land, Vested Land, Family Land, and Private Land ([24]Transparency International, 2020). Given that each of these categories of land have specific acquisition processes, individuals must determine the qualifications for land ownership themselves. Since most of the land in Ghana is customary land, this type of land is the most common for individuals to purchase or rent.

Historically, land transfers were completed orally with the grantees of the land expressing their gratitude with small gifts ([25]Lentz, 2011, 64). However, this system poses inherent challenges because of witnesses' deteriorating memories, lost evidence, double-selling of property, and witnesses' deaths, all of which led to frequent inter-clan disputes and ongoing litigation ([2]Ehwi and Asante, 2016). The current informal process of land ownership and registration in rural communities mirrors some similar characteristics to these older systems. Institutional barriers discourage individuals from seeking formal documentation around land transfers, especially of customary lands.

Conveyancing

Conveyancing is concerned with the legal mechanisms whereby land or an interest in land is transferred from one person to another so that the land or interest becomes vested in the other people. It includes transfer of ownership in land, the rights of the parties at different stages in immovable property transactions, and the respective positions of the parties if things should go wrong in the course of the transaction.

In Ghana the method of conveyancing used in any particular case depends on whether or not the title to the land has been registered. If the land happens to have been in a title registration district as declared by the Minister, then title is used and registered but where the land is not situated in a title registration district then, deeds are used and it is the registration of the deeds that constitute the title of the owner. The bedrock of all valid conveyancing in Ghana is a good root of title.

Root of Title

In order to establish formal ownership over land in Ghana, the owner of the property must hold a root of title. A good root of title is essentially the deed of a property that can be traced to prove that the current owner has a clear title ([26]Reuters, 2022). This is used for the sale of land to determine legitimacy of the owner and the history of the property. A good root of title provides at least 15 years of the property's history, but date back much older if the property has been well established. Normally, a root of title contains information about the legal owner

and the interest in the land, a description of the property, and a clear title. For those looking to purchase unregistered land, providing a good root of title can be challenging given the informal history of ownership in the property.

Instruments

The current principal enactment on the registration of instruments is The Lands Act 2020 (Act 1036). The registration of instruments does not give validity to the instrument, instead it only gives notice of the tool being used. The law provides that any instrument may be registered under the Act. An instrument shall not be registered unless it contains a description which is sufficient to the registrar. The instrument must enable the location and boundaries of the land to be identified, or a sufficient reference to the date and particulars of registration of an instrument affecting the same land and already registered. A description may be made by reference to a plan certified by a licensed or official surveyor.

As far as the law is concerned, legal validity is attached to the registered instrument and not the title or interest transferred in that instrument. The Land Registrar is empowered to refuse to register an instrument affecting land on stated grounds (Section 106 of Act 1036) but has to notify the party wishing to register his instrument, the reason for his objection to the registration (See Section 107 of Act 1036)([27]Ghana Land-Act, 2020). No instrument shall be registered by the Land Registrar unless it has been duly stamped.

The law on stamping in Ghana is the Stamp Duty Act, 2005, Act 698 ([28]Stamp, 2005). As far as instruments are concerned, the law requires that stamping must be effected within two months of the date of execution (Section 12(1) of the Stamp Duty Act). The instrument to be stamped must be accompanied with a statement in the form set out in the Second Schedule of Act 689. After submission of the instrument to the Lands Commission, the Commissioner shall assess the duties payable on an instrument required to be stamped under this Act. The law further provides that failure to stamp the instrument within the stipulated period of two months will attract a penalty (Section 12(2) of Act 689). Stamping is a conditional precedent to the acceptance of an instrument for registration.

Major Challenges to Land Administration

Due to the complexities of land registration systems, authorities can take advantage of these loopholes for monetary gain. Due to inefficient legislation, authorities have been able to do so for decades. While there are certainly nuanced issues that contribute to the general failure of the system, the central issue can be distilled into three words— poor record keeping ([10]Mintah et al., 2020, 160; [11] Mintah et al., 2021, 1). Ownership connotes possession of and title to land. However, proof of ownership can be documentary or mere possession in the absence of adverse claim or better title.

The two land administration systems within Ghana do not communicate well with each other. Traditional processes are necessary to acquire land rights on the majority of land in Ghana yet the state system does not formally recognize the records generated by those processes.

Instead, the responsibility falls to the individual to navigate these complex systems and complete the necessary steps to satisfy both.

For example, a villager may approach their chief and acquire the rights to farm a parcel of their community's customary land. This right takes the form of a lease and allows the villager to develop and benefit from the land for the duration of that lease.

While the villagers may have been issued documentation of their transaction by the chief, the formal land administration offices did not receive any record of it. The responsibility falls on that individual to formalize, or "perfect", their land rights. This is an involved process that includes acquiring necessary documentation from their customary authority, hiring a surveyor to establish their land boundaries, hiring a lawyer to submit the legal documentation, paying various administrative fees, and paying for travel costs if any of these steps are outside of their immediate community.

Whether the steps are too many, the time required too great, or simply because it costs too much, current research has clearly shown that many Ghanaians go without formally registering their land rights with the state. It is estimated that four-fifths of all land in Ghana is unregistered ([29]RICS, 2018). Without formal registration, landowners are vulnerable to various land tenure risks, such as land encroachments, multiple sale of land parcels, and competing interests in land.

This has led to a high number of land tenure disputes in Ghana. For example, in two communities surveyed, 60% of all court cases were related to land disputes ([30] Asaaga, 2021, 6). These often take years to settle and can result in the original land rights holder losing their case due to bureaucratic, record-keeping idiosyncrasies. Those unable to pursue legal aid, or those who find the wait untenable, often resort to violent confrontations in order to protect their land rights. The burden that these issues place on the citizens of Ghana have been characterized as a leading contributor to the country's inability to improve critical infrastructure.

Ghana is not the only country struggling with improving its land registry systems. Many hundreds of millions of dollars of international development funding has been made available over recent decades to modernize and digitize land administration systems in the Global South. Too often, these projects are driven by top-down, centralized systems that attempt to deploy architectures and practices that are in place in the Global North. They have not been sufficiently informed by a bottom-up understanding of customary land tenure practices. This is clearly the case in Ghana where the current regulations are inadequate for capturing all of the various customary transactions. As a result, the national land registration system is left inaccurate and not up-to-date on the current land transfers taking place on customary land.

The failure of various efforts to marry a western style legal structure to the customary principles surrounding land tenure has become a burden primarily felt by those caught between the two—the citizens. Individuals seeking to safeguard their land rights must undergo a lengthy and costly process of acquiring the appropriate documentation, traveling to various offices, and paying multiple fees in order to achieve formal registration with the state ([31] Ubink and Quan, 2008, 204-205). The only reason any of these individuals choose to suffer through this maze of bureaucracy is because of the historically vulnerable nature of land tenure security in the country

([32] Imani, 2020)— and not all have the resources required despite this ongoing threat. These rights holders are also aware that there's a risk that the same parcel sold to them could be sold again by the customary authority to another party who, if having greater resources, could beat them to formal registration or take them to court to argue who made the purchase first.

Conclusion

Understanding land registration and administrative processes in Ghana can be an arduous task, leaving individuals feeling discouraged. This is problematic as formal land registration can be used as a means to lift communities out of poverty and expand economic opportunities for individual land owners.

For too long, centralized, top-down approaches have dominated the legal and regulatory environment. Often, this is exacerbated in land registration and administrative systems. Decentralized, blockchain-based solutions offer exciting possibilities to modernize these systems of record-keeping. This is pertinent for individuals living on the ground seeking opportunities to inform system planning, design, and implementation. These challenges come to a head in Ghana, where the land registration system is quickly being outpaced by technological innovation and faces issues around capacity, legacy systems, and time-constraints. While the literature extensively covers the situation in Ghana from the view of investors, developers, and the state, less is available from the customary view which is critical to achieving broad stakeholder buy-in; Landano has identified this challenge and is working to mitigate it through on the ground partnerships with the communities and their leadership.

The Landano project aims to offer a solution to these challenges by creating a trustworthy land record system which can be offered to countries that are struggling to provide secure land tenure rights. Landano has piloted an innovative project that has been informed and designed by community members. The MVP proof-of-concept creates opportunities for individuals to own, securely store, and manage their own land-based documents. This provides a type of financial autonomy that is currently unavailable and could be leveraged to pave the way for financial freedom and options, allowing people to invest in their careers and communities.

The decentralized record keeping system introduced by landano creates, archives, and validates land right records by minting them as unique Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) which have ownership information embedded in their coding to aid in traceability. These records can be designed to align with local cultural practices as well as laws for land administration and digital evidence. The Landano mission is to create a system that allows these NFTs to be cheaply and reliably minted in order to aid traditional community leaders in their constitutional responsibilities. Rights-holders who use these trustworthy Landano records will be able to utilize them as collateral and equity for new DeFi lending opportunities where previously there was very limited financial service options. Therefore, Landano stands to make a significant impact on social and financial inclusion for a wide range of previously undocumented, unbanked individuals.

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